

Studies on Oxidation. Part II. Action of Ferric Chloride and Hydrogen Peroxide on Symmetrical and Unsymmetrical Di-substituted Thiocarbamides and the Synthesis of Thiodiazoles.

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In Part I of this series it has been shown by one of us (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 269) that thiodiazoles of different types can be obtained by the action of suitable oxidising agents on aldehyde and ketone-thiosemicarbazones. In the present paper our object is to extend the work in this direction by preparing a few more thiodiazoles by oxidising the various diarylthiocarbamides, the course of reaction being represented according to the following scheme :

that is, the thiocarbamide is probably first oxidised to a disulphide (I) which is not possible to isolate and this then undergoes further oxidation to yield the thiodiazole (II) with the separation of one atom of sulphur.

Hector (*Ber.*, 1889, 22, 1177; 1890, 23, 357) has already described the preparation of certain thiodiazoles obtained from the action of oxidising agents on the monosubstituted arylthiocarbamides on the lines postulated above. Further, Hegershoff (*Ber.*, 1903, 36, 3121) and later on, Hunter (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 2023, 2270; etc.) in a series of papers have recorded the interesting observations on the conversion of symmetrical diarylthiocarbamides through the agency of bromine into arylaminobenzothiazoles by way of perbromides, which on treatment with sulphurous acid is rapidly reduced, the bromine being eliminated as hydrogen bromide and the free base

formed. The following example will illustrate the mechanism of the reaction :

Here also the action of bromine may in the first phase be regarded as an oxidising effect removing two atoms of hydrogen from the thiocarbamide, *viz.* one atom from the benzene nucleus and the other from the thiol group; and in the second phase the unsaturated compound takes up more bromine to form perbromide.

All these curious observations made it a point of interest to investigate into the action of oxidising agents on the disubstituted arylthiocarbamides and thus to extend the reaction to the preparation of thiodiazole derivatives (II) and, therefore, the oxidising action of hydrogen peroxide and of ferric chloride on the diarylthiocarbamides in water or alcohol was studied. Under conditions analogous to these employed in the previous cases, symmetrical or asymmetrical diarylthiocarbamides readily passed into thiodiazole derivatives when hydrogen peroxide was used as the oxidising agent; but with ferric chloride the symmetrical diarylthiocarbamides were in most part decomposed to yield the respective mustard oils which were distilled and identified and in the original solutions were obtained guanidine derivatives together with tar and in no case the formation of the thiodiazoles could be traced. Consequently the action of ferric chloride on the thiocarbamides has not been described in the experimental part. Thus hydrogen peroxide is found to be very suitable in oxidising these compounds as this method gives a tolerably good yield and gives no difficulty in isolating the thiodiazoles.

EXPERIMENTAL.

2:5-Diphenylimido-3:4-diphenyl-1:3:4-thiodiazole (Formula II, R=Ph).

Symmetrical diphenylthiourea (5 g.) was gently boiled with 50 c. c. of alcohol under reflux in a flask on the water-bath until it went into solution. The flask was then taken out and fitted with a cork through which was inserted a separating funnel which contained

3.5 gms. (a little more than one atom of oxygen required for one molecule of thiocarbamide) of perhydrol diluted with ten times of water. After the solution in the flask had sufficiently cooled and crystals had just begun to separate from the solution, the perhydrol solution was slowly added from the separating funnel with continuous shaking. Heat was evolved and sulphur precipitated. Some of the alcohol was then boiled off, sulphur removed and from the solution crystals separated on long standing. These were collected and recrystallised from rectified spirit; m. p. 228°-230°: (Found: N, 13.44; C, 74.51; H, 4.94; S, 7.83. $C_{26}H_{20}N_4S$ requires N, 13.33; C, 74.28; H, 4.76; and S, 7.62 per cent.).

2:5-Di *p*-tolylimido-3:4-di-*p*-tolyl-1:3:4-thiodiazole.—It was prepared as before using sym-di-*p*-tolylthiocarbamide with the difference that in this case the reaction product was thrown out of solution within a few minutes as a white amorphous substance. It was boiled under reflux for 15 minutes more with the addition of alcohol and filtered hot. The substance was then crystallised thrice from acetic acid; m. p. 261°: (Found: N, 11.34. $C_{30}H_{28}N_4S$ requires N, 11.76 per cent.).

2:5-Di-*o*-tolylimido-3:4-di-*o*-tolyl-1:3:4-thiodiazole.—It was prepared from symmetrical di-*o*-tolylthiocarbamide and perhydrol in exactly the same way as the above compound. The white substance obtained was crystallised from acetic acid when it melted at 249°. (Found: N, 11.59. $C_{30}H_{28}N_4S$ requires N, 11.76 per cent.).

2:5-Di-*m*-xylylimino-3:4-di-*m*-xylyl-1:3:4-thiodiazole.—With the slow progress of reaction which began on warming the mixture of the thiocarbamide and perhydrol, the sym-*m*-xylylthiocarbamide went into solution and after a short time the reaction product was precipitated as a white crystalline powder. This was crystallised thrice from alcohol (large volume); m. p. 247°. (Found: N, 10.67. $C_{34}H_{36}N_4S$ requires N, 10.53 per cent.).

2:5-Di α -naphthylimino-3:4-di- α -naphthyl-1:3:4-thiodiazole.—To a hot suspension of sym-di- α -naphthylthiocarbamide in alcohol was added perhydrol when no reaction took place. The mixture was, therefore, boiled under reflux for a few minutes when the reaction commenced as was shown by a sudden change of appearance of the thiocarbamide. Heating was discontinued shortly after this (too much of heating should be avoided as the solid is thereby changed into a tarry mass) and the reaction product was crystallised thrice from acetic acid and obtained as a white substance which melted to a dark

liquid at 285°. (Found: N, 9.14. $C_{42}H_{28}N_4S$ requires N, 9.03 per cent.).

2:5-Di-β-naphthylimino-3:4-di-β-naphthyl-1:3:4-thiodiazole.—It was obtained from sym.-β:β-dinaphthylthiocarbamide and perhydrol by a method similar to that described in the case of the α-compound as a white substance which after crystallisation from acetic acid shrinks and changes in colour at 268° and melts at 288° to a dark liquid. (Found: N, 9.17. $C_{42}H_{28}N_4S$ requires N, 9.03 per cent.).

2:5-Di-(phenylmethylamino)-1:3:4-thiodiazole.—Prepared as before from unsym-phenylmethylthiocarbamide in alcohol, the reaction product did not separate from the solution which, however, became a little turbid owing to the separation of sulphur. The solution was, therefore, concentrated to about one-fourth of its volume but still no precipitate was obtained. The solution was then exposed to air to allow the alcohol to evaporate when a substance was left behind in the form of a syrupy liquid. This was dissolved in ether, and as the ether evaporated off the reaction product separated in a solid crystalline form. It was then crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and water; m. p. 94°. (Found: N, 18.98. $C_{16}H_{16}N_4S$ requires N, 18.92 per cent.).

2:5-Di-(phenylethylamino)-1:3:4-thiodiazole.—The oily product obtained from unsym-phenylethyl-thiocarbamide and perhydrol according to the foregoing method was dissolved in ether from which it was obtained as a white crystalline mass. This was collected and recrystallised from dilute spirit; m. p. 107°-109°. (Found: N, 17.41. $C_{16}H_{20}N_4S$ requires N, 17.28 per cent.).

2:5-Di-(diphenylamino)-1:3:4-thiodiazole.—Oxidised as before unsym-diphenylthiocarbamide gradually dissolved forming a clear solution from which the reaction product was thrown out of solution as a yellowish precipitate. The mixture was allowed to cool, filtered and the residue crystallised thrice from alcohol; m. p. 155°. (Found: N, 13.49. $C_{26}H_{20}N_4S$ requires N, 13.33 per cent.).

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